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Sociodemographic Characteristics of Fish Stakeholders At The Landing Sites of Challawa Reservoir, Kano State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to examine some characteristics of fish stakeholders (fishermen and middlemen) at the landing site of Challawa Reservoir Kano State, Nigeria. A total of seven landing sites were identified out of which three landing sites with the highest fishing activities were purposively selected for the study. Information such as gender, education level, religion, age, tribe, fishing gears and years of experience were collected using a set of structured questionnaire from 47 fishermen and 14 middlemen. The result shows that 100% of the respondents were male, 64.3% and 53.2% of the middlemen and fishermen respectively fall between the ages of 26-40 years, 57.1% and 61.7% of the middlemen and fishermen respectively have experience of over 10 years, 57.1% of the middlemen have primary education while 80.9% of the fishermen have Qur'anic education only. The fishermen at Challawa Reservoir are classified as artisanal fisheries as a result of their characteristics, cultural and religious reasons limit the participation of women in fishing activities as such it became a male dominated occupation with respondents of middle age group dominating the stakeholders. There is need for the government to look into the educational aspect of the people and also organize training sessions that will help them carry out their fishing activities properly.

Keywords: Reservoir, stakeholders landing sites, middlemen, respondents, artisanal, Challawa Reservoir Kano State

INTRODUCTION

Fish production in Nigeria comes from three sources; artisanal (inland rivers, lakes, coastal and brackish water), aquaculture (fish farm) and industrial fishing. However, Nigeria is blessed with about 14 million hectares of reservoirs, lake, ponds and main rivers capable of producing over 980,000 metric tons of fish annually (FDF, 2007). Majority of these reservoirs are built on seasonal rivers. Nigerian fish production has fluctuated between industrial fishing, inland aquaculture, and artisanal fishing (FDF, 2008). Statistical surveys have shown that the demand for fish in the country based on the 2014 population estimate of 180m is 3.32 million metric tons, the domestic fish production from Aquaculture, Artisanal and industrial fishing for 2014 is 1.123 million metric tons leaving a deficit of 2.197 million metric tons. In addition, in 2014 fisheries contributed 0.48% to the Agriculture GDP (FDF, 2016).

However, the majority of the fish supply in the developing world, comes from the artisanal fisheries sector, which is the most significant sector. However, artisanal fishing is characterized by low technology, lack of contemporary equipment, lack of funding to expand, etc., which leads to post-harvest loss, labor-intensive industry, and few or no chances for expansion.

Among these reservoirs is the Challawa Reservoir which is located at Karaye Local Government Area of Kano State about 90 km southwest of Kano city in Northern Nigeria. The dam was started by the Water Resources and Engineering Construction Agency (WRECA) of the Kano State Government, and was later handed over to the Federal Government under the auspices of Hadejia-Jama'are River Basin Development Authority (HJRBDA) who contract it to Julius Berger, a German-based construction firm who completed it in 1992. The Federal Government of Nigeria provided funding for the dam, which is owned by the Hadejia Jama'are River Basin Development Authority. The dam was built across the Challawa River, which empties into Lake Chad in north-eastern Nigeria.

Around the state capital, the dam was first built for agriculture, water supply, hydroelectricity, flood control, recreational fishing, and the preservation of wild species. With a capacity of 904 million m³, the Challawa Gorge Dam is the second-largest dam supplying water to the city of Kano. The dam is 7.8 km (5 miles) long and 42 m (138 ft) high. The project essentially consisted of a homogeneous dam of decomposed rock. Core drilling performed at the dam's center, however, detected the existence of various seams in the under laying rock which made it necessary to construct an anti-seepage grout curtain. The dam also includes construction of a 30 m (98 ft) intake tower, intake main and a 600 m (1 967 ft) long spillway. Following completion, the Tiga and Challawa Gorge dams controlled more than 80% of the Hadejia river system, one of the main water sources for the Hadejia-Nguru Wetlands in the Lake Chad basin. The Hadejia Valley Irrigation Project, the Kano River Irrigation Project and the Kano City Water Supply (KCWS) are all supplied with water from these two dams. There are settlements along the Challawa Gorge Dam where farming, raising livestock, and artisanal fishing are the main occupation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was carried out in Kano State, Nigeria at Challawa Reservoir which is located at Karaye Local Government Area of Kano State as shown in Figure 1, about 90 km southwest of Kano city, at latitude 8°06'58.04"E and longitude 11°41'21.95"N (Google Earth, 2016). It is a significant reservoir on the Challawa River, which is a tributary of the Kano River, which is the Hadejia River's principal tributary (Uyigue, 2009).

The dam was constructed in the year 1990 to 1992 by Julius Berger Nigeria using rock fill construction. It has a height of 42 m and a length of 7.8 km. The reservoir has a full storage capacity of 904,000,000 m³. The direct catchment area is 3857 km² (World Bank, Lake Chad Basin Commission, 2002). It is used for irrigation; fishing, and township water supply, it was also constructed with hydropower potential of around 3MW (Salihi, 2009).

Due to lack of documented information about the landing sites along Challawa reservoir, each of the landing sites were visited, and the co-ordinate for each site were recorded using Verizon GPS meter.

A total of seven landing sites were identified along Challawa reservoir, where six out of the seven (Turawa, Feginma, Tinqis, Hammasare, Damagari and Romonkunne) falls under Karaye Local Government Area while the seventh (Sakarma) falls under Kiru Local Government Area. All the landing sites are surrounded by farmland as a result of the fertile land which surrounds the water body.

The fishing activity carried out on these sites varies, where Turawa, Sakarma and Feginma have higher fishing activities when compared to the other sites. In addition to fishing, other activities carried out on these landing sites include animal grazing, hawking by food vendors and recreation for it serves as a gathering or resting ground for fishermen and farmers.

Figure 1: Map of Challawa Reservoir Showing the Position of Each Landing Site

Table 1: Landing Sites Along Challawa Reservoir and Their Co-ordinates

Names of landing site	Co-ordinates
Turawa	11°40'52.4"N 008°02'31.9"E
Sakarma	11°39'54.3"N 008°00'61.1"E
Feginma	11°39'28.1"N 007°58'18.9"E
Tinqis	11°45'27.23"N 8°00'16.85"E
Hammasare	11°39'42.49"N 7°58'18.30"E
Damagari	11°43'28.64"N 7°59'42.80"E
Romonkunne	11°39'00.53"N 7°57'21.51"E

Sampling Method

Both purposive and random sampling procedures were employed in this study. Three landing sites with the highest fishing activities were purposively selected out of the seven sites identified. Random sampling was employed to choose respondents from each site, thus the sampling frame for the data collection included middlemen and fishermen. (Dambatta and Sogbesan, 2015).

Data Collection

The data was collected through the aid of questionnaire in the form of structured interview, the questions were prepared in closed ended form to collect relevant information concerning the stakeholders' socio-demographic characteristics.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics was used to analysed the socio demographic characteristics of the stakeholders.

RESULT

A total of 47 fishermen and 14 middlemen were involved in this study as shown in table 2 and table 3. In the three landing sites sampled (Turawa, Sakarma and Feginma) all the fishermen and middlemen encountered were males, Hausa by tribe, Muslim and had no formal training. With regards to age of the fishermen, 23.4% are less than 25 years while 53.2% were in the age group of 26-40, 14.9% represent the age group of 41-55, and the age range of 55 and above are the least with 8.5%. As for the middlemen, 64.3% were in the age group of 26-40 while 35.7% represent the age range of 41-55.

In terms of experience, the fishermen with experience from 1-10 years were 38.3%, those with experience of 11-20 years were also 38.3% while the rest had experience of 21-30 years and above 30 years, and as for the middlemen 57.1% had experience of above 10 years, 20.6% had experience of 6-10 years while 14.3% had experience of 1-5 years. The result also indicated that the educational qualification of the fishermen and middlemen were mainly primary and quranic with 19.1% and 80.9% of the fishermen respectively then 57.1% and 28.6% of the middlemen respectively. Although, 14.3% of the middlemen had secondary education.

Four types of fishing gear were identified during the study period: this include traps, long lines, gill nets, and cast nets. The most used fishing gear is the gillnet with 42.6% followed by long line with 14.9%, the least used gear is trap with 10.6%. Although, 19.1% make use of all four gears. With respect to buyers, 93.6% of the fishermen sold their catch to the middlemen while 6.4% sold theirs to the processors. And as for the middlemen, they all sold their product to the marketers.

Table 2: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Fishermen at Challawa Reservoir

S/NO.	VARIABLES	FREQUENCY			TOTAL	PERCENTAGE (%)
		TURAWA (13)	SAKARMA (19)	FEGINMA (15)		
1.	Gender					
	Male	13	19	15	47	100
	Female	-	-	-	-	-
2.	Age					
	<25	3	4	4	11	23.4
	26-40	7	10	8	25	53.2
	41-55	2	3	2	7	14.9
	> 55	1	2	1	4	8.5
3.	Marital status					
	Single	2	3	2	7	14.9
	Married	11	16	13	40	85.1
4.	Religion					
	Islam	13	19	15	47	100
	Christianity	-	-	-	-	-
5.	Tribe					
	Hausa	13	19	15	47	100
	Fulani	-	-	-	-	-
	Others	-	-	-	-	-
6.	Years of experience					
	1-10 years	5	5	8	18	38.3
	11-20 years	5	9	4	18	38.3
	21-30 years	2	3	2	7	14.9
	Above 30 years	1	2	1	4	8.5

7.	Education					
	Primary	3	2	4	9	19.1
	Secondary	-	-	-	-	-
	Tertiary	-	-	-	-	-
	Quranic	10	17	11	38	80.9
8.	Types of gear					
	Cast net	2	3	1	6	12.8
	Gill net	5	8	7	20	42.6
	Long line	2	2	3	7	14.9
	Traps	1	2	2	5	10.6
	All of the above	3	4	2	9	19.1
9.	Buyers					
	Middlemen	12	17	15	44	93.6
	Consumers	-	-	-	-	-
	Processor	1	2	-	3	6.4

Table 3: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Middlemen at Challawa Reservoir

S/NO.	VARIABLE	FREQUENCY			TOTAL	PERCENTAGE (%)
		TURAWA (4)	SAKARMA (7)	FEGINMA (3)		
1.	Gender					
	Male	4	7	3	14	100
	Female	-	-	-	-	-
2.	Age					
	<25	-	-	-	-	-
	26-40	2	5	2	9	64.3
	41-55	2	2	1	5	35.7
	> 55	-	-	-	-	-
3.	Marital status					
	Single	-	-	-	-	-
	Married	4	7	3	14	100
4.	Religion					
	Islam	4	7	3	14	100
	Christianity	-	-	-	-	-
5.	Tribe					
	Haussa	4	7	3	14	100
	Fulani	-	-	-	-	-
	Others	-	-	-	-	-
6.	Education					
	Primary	1	4	3	8	57.1
	Secondary	2	-	-	2	14.3
	Tertiary	-	-	-	-	-
	Quranic	1	3	-	4	28.6
7.	Years of experience					
	1-5 years	1	1	-	2	14.3
	6-10 years	1	2	1	4	28.6
	Above 10 years	2	4	2	8	57.1
8	Training of fish quality					
	Yes	-	-	-	-	-
	No	4	7	3	14	100
9	Buyers					
	Consumers	-	-	-	-	-
	Marketers	4	7	3	14	100

DISCUSSION

As a result of their characteristics, the fisherman at Challawa Reservoir are categorized as artisanal fisheries, which is comparable to other small-scale fishermen in Nigeria. The fishermen typically catch small amounts of fish, but enough for their own use and small-scale commercial purposes because they use basic fishing gear and equipment. Similarly, Bawa *et al.* (2019) reported in his work ‘Socio economic characteristics of artisanal fishermen in inland waters of Kebbi state’ that fishermen at Kebbi State also belongs to the group of artisanal fishermen.

The fishing activities at Challawa Reservoir is dominated by males as a result of cultural and religious reasons, which limits the participation of women in fishing activities. Similar observation was reported by

Aminu *et al.* (2019) on Preliminary Survey of Some Sociodemographic Characteristics of Fishermen in Dundaye Flood Plain, At Kwalkwalawa Rima River Sokoto Nigeria and Bawa *et al.* (2019) on Socio economic characteristics of artisanal fishermen in inland waters of Kebbi state, North-West Nigeria. Contrary to this research findings, Olapade (2012) reported that women play some significant roles in artisanal fisheries in Asejire River, in the state of Oyo, Nigeria.

Meanwhile, the data obtained in this study shows that the middle age group dominates the stakeholders with the age range of 26-40 years This age group comprises the creative, driven, and flexible population, and because there aren't many other employments in the community for this age group, it's likely that those in this age range will continue in this line of work, this is similar with the findings of Aminu *et al.*, (2019) in their work 'Preliminary Survey of

Some Sociodemographic Characteristics of Fishermen in Dundaye Flood Plain, At Kwalkwalawa Rima River Sokoto Nigeria' where they reported that the middle age group constitute the highest percentage with 40%.

The gear types used in this present study are gill nets, cast nets, hook and line (Long line), Traps (Gura trap). All these gear types have been acknowledged by Bawa *et al.* (2019). They were also the most common fishing gears used by the artisanal fishermen in the Kainji Lake and the Lake Chad basin in Nigeria (Béné *et al* 2004). Gill net is considered as the most significant and the most used fishing gear among the fishers with 42.6% of the fishermen using it. This is due to its efficiency, affordability, and ability to capture more economically valuable fish than other artisanal gear.

CONCLUSION

The socio-demographic characteristics of the fish stakeholders at Challawa Reservoir can be classified as 'artisanal fisheries' and are similar to other artisanal fishermen in Nigeria. This study will provide some basic data and information to the government and other organizations in Kano State who are in charge of managing the inland waters and its fishery resources. This also would be useful for future fisheries planning and research.

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